

Call for manuscripts

We are calling for short original fantasy stories conveying the spirit of the **New European Bauhaus**. We want authors and artists to imagine and build a beautiful and liveable future, the world we dream about.

The winning manuscript will become the **1st Möbius Book**, a cross-media experience involving a 3D audio, virtual reality production, and art installation!

1,500€
in kind prize will
be awarded to the
first place*

Apply before
15/01/2022

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Eligibility criteria

Original and unpublished work.

Maximum length of 6000 characters (including spaces) and maximum two (2) submission per author..

Participants must be of legal age (>18) and citizens and/or residents of EU-27 countries, plus associated countries or in process of becoming associated to Horizon Europe.

You can submit your work in English, Italian or Spanish.

*500€ for second and third places – The prizes are in kind and authors will receive the amount as a voucher redeemable at an online or physical store in their respective country of residence.

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#mobiusbook

